

Recruitment Process Experience Survey – Recruitment Process THRIVE Project (CoARA Boost, Second Cascade Funding)

We want to hear from you! This survey is designed to help us look at our recruitment and selection process. Your feedback will help us ensure our recruitment process is supportive, responsible, and aligned with the ARRA principles for the reform of research assessment.

If you want to know more about the ARRA commitments, please check out the details here.

1. How clear did you find the job description and what would be expected of you? (1) Not clear at all — (5) Very clear
2. Did the different steps of our selection process were explained in a way that was easy to follow? (1) Strongly disagree — (5) Strongly agree
3. Did you feel well-informed about the criteria we used to evaluate your application? (1) Not informed at all — (5) Very well informed
4. Did you feel that the selection process provided a fair and comprehensive assessment of your professional skills and experience? (1) Strongly disagree — (5) Strongly agree
5. Did you feel that your qualitative strengths (such as your motivation, leadership potential, and future capabilities) were valued? (1) Not at all — (5) To a great extent
6. Did you feel that you had the opportunity to demonstrate your abilities beyond traditional or quantitative metrics (e.g., beyond just publication counts or grades)? (1) Strongly disagree — (5) Strongly agree
7. If applicable, were you able to comfortably discuss contextual factors in your career, such as transitions, breaks, or non-linear paths? Long answer text
8. How well do you think the interviews and assessments align with the actual day-to-day requirements of the position? (1) Not aligned at all — (5) Perfectly aligned
9. Did you feel the process valued your unique profile rather than looking for a single "standard" or specific candidate type? (1) Strongly disagree — (5) Strongly agree
10. If you received feedback, how helpful and constructive did you find it for your future professional development? (1) Not helpful — (5) Extremely helpful
11. Was there any stage where you felt you didn't have enough information or weren't fully able to showcase your potential? Yes/No
12. (If yes) Please tell us which stage this was and what we could do better. Long answer text
13. Overall, how would you describe your experience with our selection process at IRB Barcelona?
14. In your view, how could we improve our selection processes? Long answer text